

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF WORKPLACE STRESS OF TEACHER EDUCATORS OF NAAC ACCREDITED AND NON-ACCREDITED TEACHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS OF ROHILKHAND REGION

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ABSTRACT

This study is conducted to compare the workplace stress of teacher educators of NAAC Accredited and non-Accredited teacher education institutions. The Teacher's workplace stress scale developed by Dr Ramandeep Kaur Sidhu and Dr Manu Chandha (2016) was adopted for the present study and descriptive survey research method employed in the present study. A sample of teacher educators of teacher education institutions were selected from Rohilkhand region using simple random sampling technique. Statistical techniques such as mean, standard deviation, and t-test were employed for the analysis of data. The analyzed results revealed that 1. There is significant difference found in Teacher's work place stress between male teacher educators of NAAC Accredited and non-Accredited teacher education institutions, 2. There is significant difference found in Teacher's workplace stress between female teacher educators of NAAC Accredited and non-Accredited teacher education institutions, 3. There is significant difference found in Teacher's workplace stress between more experienced teacher educators of NAAC Accredited and non-Accredited teacher education institutions, 4. There is significant difference found in Teacher's workplace stress between less experienced teacher educators of NAAC Accredited and non-Accredited teacher education institutions.

KEYWORDS: Teacher's workplace stress, Teacher Educators, NAAC Accredited and Non-Accredited Teacher Education Institutions.

INTRODUCTION

In the society, teachers play a crucial role. Teachers are held in great regard by the public for their behaviour, competence, knowledge, and skills. One method used to evaluate a country's potential and worth is through the work of its teachers. Academic experts and scholars concur that teaching is a delicate social vocation that is extremely important and forms the basis for all other professions worldwide. Teaching is a distinct and an important profession in this world because all other professions grow and are sustained due to this profession. Teachers are expected to produce logical thinkers who will contribute important and effective inputs for a society. Teachers are also base stones for the advancement and development of the society. Today, education is becoming a business where teachers are under-paid employees like other industries and students are the customers. This badly affects the teacher's mental health and creates job stress. Stress is an emotional response towards any condition that affects any individual's health. According to Selye (1978), stress can be defined as an inner force or outer actions that disturb the individual stability.

Stress is defined as a person's reaction to negative emotions that threaten their self-respect, such as annoyance and powerlessness. Particularly, job stress is related with mental stress and pressure that is associated with worker's capabilities to react and handle any situation at their workplace thoughtfully (Kyriacou & Sutcliffe, 1978). In another words, it is related with all those dangerous emotional responses of employees where their skills and abilities are not well matched with job demands (Chen & Silverthorne, 2008). Workload, organizational constraints, problems in the classroom, and interpersonal conflicts are the major factors that contribute to teacher's workplace stress. Role conflict, role ambiguity, workload, and workplace conflict are factors of workplace stress known as stressors (Addae, Parbooteah & Velinor, 2008).

Teacher's workplace stress level is also increased when they do not get proper social status in the economy. A teacher is regarded as a person with high- quality skill but no standard power. Das et al. (2012) is of the view that teachers are normally disappointed with their societal status. However, these situations have become a foundation of societal distress, where teachers believe that there is no proper system of improving social status associated to their profession (Humphrey, 2002).

Workplace stress negatively affects teacher's job performance which creates lower job satisfaction and decreased quality of output (Tetrick & LaRocco, 1987). Teacher's job performance is significantly important for organizations, individuals, colleges, and university education alike. Individuals feel self-efficacy, satisfaction, and motivated when tasks are properly accomplished by showing high performance (Sonnentag et al., 2010). There are many definitions of job performance which shows the complication and complicated nature of the concept. Selamat, et al. (2013) defined teacher's job performance to be how teachers behave while teaching and it is directly related with teacher's workplace stress.

A faculty member in higher education who oversees teacher preparation is referred to as a "teacher educator. A Teacher Educator can be defined as a professional who provides education to teachers. "A teacher educator is a qualified professional who is in charge of preparing and supervising teachers in the field of education" according to Good's C.V. dictionary of education.

For Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), NAAC certification is crucial since it helps them obtain funding from different government agencies. It also enables educational establishments to evaluate their standing in relation to other establishments in the community. The NAAC is an independent entity that was created by UGC of India with the purpose of evaluating and granting accreditation to higher education establishments within the nation. NCTE ensures quality standards by monitoring, while AA and NAAC also contribute to upholding these standards (Jena and Mohanty, 2019).

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

From the discussions mentioned above it is obvious that certainly higher level of educator's workplace stress creates an attitude of apathy, lack of involvement and refusing to collaborate which leads to low quality of education, increase in wastage, increase in expenses, work failure, poor performance and strained relation of educators with the management and with other educators.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Rajesh and Kumar (2023) conducted a study on 'Teacher's workplace Stress among School Teachers – A Study Report'. The sample of this study consisted of 325 teachers from 30 schools based on their experience in government, government aided and private higher secondary school. The respondents were divided into three groups, below 30 years, 31 to 50 years, 50 years and above. Significant differences appeared between the groups of over 50 and under 30 years old, according to the results of the Tukey's W multiple comparison analysis. This demonstrated that those under the age of 30 were more committed to their jobs. They spent their free time doing job-related activities, and they finished their work even if it took longer than expected. There were also significant differences

between age and the Teacher's workplace stress dimension. According to the findings, significant differences was found in the Tukey's-W multiple comparison analysis between the group of 31-50 years old and under 30 years old. The study showed that a group of teachers below 30 years were quite satisfied with their job among the three groups and also, they were interested and like the job.

Khan et al. (2022) aimed to assess the perceived sources of teacher's workplace stress among teachers with respect to gender The sample of the study consisted of 100 teachers from Aligarh District (males=64, females=36) belonging to various schools. The result revealed that male and female teachers significantly differs in Unreasonable group and Political pressure (UG & PP), Role Overload (RO), Role Ambiguity (RA), Under Participation (UR), Impoverishment (IMP), Unprofitability (UF), Poor Peer Relation (PPR), and Overall teacher's workplace Stress and whereas no significant difference was found between male and female teachers in Responsible for person (RP), Powerlessness (PL), Role Conflict (RC), Low Status (LS) and Strenuous Working Condition (SWC).

Paul and Jain (2020). conducted a study to assess the occupational or job stress of physical education teachers in Jammu and Kashmir. The sample of the study consisted of male and female physical education teachers working in government and public schools in Jammu and Kashmir. To collect the data, the researchers used the Teachers' Occupational Stress Scale (TOSS) with the participants. It included the dimensions of the workload of teachers, students' misbehaviour, lack of professional recognition, lack of classroom resources, and poor colleague relations. The collected data was analyzed using descriptive statistics. The findings of the study revealed that there was a significant difference in the levels of occupational stress of physical education teachers concerning their gender and the type of schools. PE teachers of public schools had high stress in comparison to that of public schools. The female PE teachers of public schools had a high level of occupational stress. It might be due to stress-related health problems, lowered work productivity, inability to cope with work stress, job change considerations, and heavy workload.

Seema & Kumari (2019) in their research study titled Occupational Stress among Secondary School Teachers in relation to Gender and Types of School used Descriptive Survey Method. One hundred and twenty secondary school teachers of secondary and senior secondary schools of Rohtak district were taken up on the basis of stratified random sampling technique. Occupational Stress Index (OSI) Hindi/English by A.K. Srivastava and A.P. Singh was used to collect the data. The findings revealed that (i) No, significant difference was found between male and female secondary school teachers on Occupational Stress; (ii) Government secondary school teachers were found to have less job stress than private school teachers.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

To find out the significant difference if any the workplace stress of teacher educators of NAAC accredited and non- accredited teacher education institutions with respect to their sex (Female and Male) and Teaching Experience (More-experienced and Less-experienced).

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

The following hypotheses were formulated

1. There is no significant difference between male teacher educators of NAAC accredited and non-accredited teacher education institutions in relation to stress.
2. There is no significant difference between female teacher educators of NAAC accredited and non-accredited teacher education institutions in relation to stress.
3. There is no significant difference between more experienced teacher educators of NAAC accredited and non-accredited teacher education institutions in relation stress.

4. There is no significant difference between less experienced teacher educators of NAAC accredited and non-accredited teacher education institutions in relation to stress.

METHODOLOGY

The researcher used a descriptive survey method to investigate the current issue.

SAMPLE & SAMPLING

The researcher chose every district of Rohilkhand Region in the Uttar Pradesh to examine the current issue. There are about 145 teacher training institutions in Rohilkhand region (Bareilly, Bijnor, Budaun, Jyotiba Phule Nagar, Moradabad, Pilibhit, Rampur, Sambhal and Shahjahanpur) affiliated to MJP Rohilkhand University, Bareilly.

In cases where the population is diverse with respect to the attributes or kind of variable being studied, stratified random sampling is employed. Out of 145 teacher education institutions, 44 teacher education institutions were randomly selected for the study.

PROCEDURE OF DATA COLLECTION

After getting permission by the Principal/ HoD's of the respective teacher education institutions, the teacher educators were contacted. The aim of the investigation was explained to them. The teacher educators were then given an explanation of the purpose of the scale. They promised that the information in their responses would remain private. It was recommended of the teacher educators to thoroughly read the directions and to seek clarification as needed. The scale had no time restriction. Still, it took around forty-five minutes to finish. Following the completion of the scale, the scoring was completed in accordance with the manual's instructions.

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUE

The investigator implemented Mean, Standard Deviation and 't'- test for differential statistical analysis of data and for testing the hypotheses.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

H.1. There is no significant difference between male teacher educators of NAAC accredited and non-accredited teacher education institutions in relation to stress.

Mean and standard deviation of teacher's workplace stress of teacher educators of teacher education institutions have been described in the Table- 1.

Table 1: Differential statistics of teacher's workplace stress of male teacher educators of NAAC Accredited and Non-Accredited teacher education institutions

Tabel 1						
Dimensions	NAAC Status	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	df
Individual Insight	NAAC Accredited	82	38.52	3.17	2.10*	196
	Non- Accredited	116	39.46	3.00		
Relationship Status	NAAC Accredited	82	39.26	3.02	1.39	196
	Non- Accredited	116	39.80	2.49		
Work life Balance	NAAC Accredited	82	40.02	2.91	1.23	196
	Non- Accredited	116	40.52	2.67		
Performed Responsibilities	NAAC Accredited	82	39.90	2.89	1.26	196

	Non- Accredited	116	40.41	2.68		
Professional Ethics	NAAC Accredited	82	40.05	3.11	1.94	196
	Non- Accredited	116	40.81	2.41		
Teacher workplace stress Total	NAAC Accredited	82	197.76	12.15	2.15*	196
	Non- Accredited	116	200.99	9.02		

(*Significance level 0.05.)

(*Significance level 0.01.)

Fig. 1: Comparison of Mean and Standard Deviation for teacher’s workplace stress of male teacher educators of NAAC Accredited and Non-Accredited teacher education institutions

Table 1. The mean, standard deviation and 't' values of overall teacher’s workplace stress and dimensions of teacher’s workplace stress as individual insight, relationship status, work life balance, performed responsibilities and professional ethics has been shown in the table. It reveals that male teacher educators of both NAAC accredited and non-accredited teacher education institutions had different mean scores on teacher’s workplace stress. The first dimension (Individual insight) of teacher’s workplace stress was found significant at the (0.05) level of confidence and other four dimensions of teacher’s workplace stress was found not significant. The values of 't' for all dimension individual insight, relationship status, work life balance, performed responsibilities and professional ethics aspects were 2.10*, 1.39, 1.23, 1.26 and 1.94 respectively and for overall teacher’s workplace stress was 2.15*. The 't' values for the first dimension and for overall teacher’s workplace stress of male teacher educators of NAAC Accredited and non-Accredited teacher education institutions was found significant at the (0.05) level of confidence. So, the hypothesis that " There is no significant difference between male teacher educators of NAAC accredited and non-accredited teacher education institutions in relation to stress” rejected.

H.2. There is no significant difference between female teacher educators of NAAC accredited and non-accredited teacher education institutions in relation to stress.

Mean and standard deviation of teacher’s workplace stress of teacher educators of teacher education institutions have been described in the Table- 2

Table 2: Differential statistics of teacher’s workplace stress of female teacher educators of NAAC Accredited and Non-Accredited teacher education institutions

Table 2						
Dimensions	NAAC Status	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	df
Individual Insight	NAAC Accredited	76	38.54	3.02	3.31**	202
	Non- Accredited	128	39.90	2.73		
Relationship Status	NAAC Accredited	76	39.72	2.48	1.95	202
	Non- Accredited	128	40.42	2.48		
Work life Balance	NAAC Accredited	76	40.38	2.40	1.02	202
	Non- Accredited	128	40.71	2.12		
Performed Responsibilities	NAAC Accredited	76	39.67	2.94	2.92**	202
	Non- Accredited	128	40.78	2.42		
Professional Ethics	NAAC Accredited	76	40.84	2.67	0.05	202
	Non- Accredited	128	40.86	2.06		
Teacher workplace stress Total	NAAC Accredited	76	199.16	9.43	3.01**	202
	Non- Accredited	128	202.67	7.13		

(*Significance level 0.05.)

(*Significance level 0.01.)

Fig. 2: Mean and Standard Deviation for teacher’s workplace stress of female teacher educators of teacher education institutions

Table 2. The mean, standard deviation and 't' values of overall teacher’s workplace stress and

dimensions of teacher's workplace stress as individual insight, relationship status, work life balance, performed responsibilities and professional ethics has been shown in the table. It reveals that female teacher educators of both NAAC accredited and non-accredited teacher education institutions had different mean scores on teacher's workplace stress. The first dimension (Individual insight) and fourth dimension (Performed responsibilities) of teacher's workplace stress was found significant at the (0.05 and 0.01) level of confidence and other three dimensions of teacher's workplace stress was found not significant. The values of 't' for individual insight, relationship status, work life balance, performed responsibilities and professional ethics aspects were 3.31**, 1.95, 1.02, 2.92** and 0.05 respectively and for overall teacher's workplace stress was 3.01**. The 't' values for the first dimension, fourth dimension and for overall teacher's workplace stress of female teacher educators of NAAC Accredited and non-Accredited teacher education institutions was found significant at the (0.05) level of confidence. So, the hypothesis that " There is no significant difference between female teacher educators of NAAC accredited and non-accredited teacher education institutions in relation to stress" rejected.

H.3. There is no significant difference between more experienced teacher educators of NAAC accredited and non-accredited teacher education institutions in relation stress.

Mean and standard deviation of teacher's workplace stress of teacher educators of teacher education institutions have been described in the Table- 3

Table 3: Differential statistics of teacher's workplace stress of more experienced teacher educators of NAAC Accredited and Non-Accredited teacher education institutions

Table 3						
Dimensions	NAAC Status	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	df
Individual Insight	NAAC Accredited	83	38.83	2.81	2.58*	219
	Non- Accredited	138	39.86	2.89		
Relationship Status	NAAC Accredited	83	39.60	2.35	2.45*	219
	Non- Accredited	138	40.41	2.41		
Worklife Balance	NAAC Accredited	83	40.37	2.56	0.76	219
	Non- Accredited	138	40.63	2.38		
Performed Responsibilities	NAAC Accredited	83	40.11	2.43	1.85	219
	Non- Accredited	138	40.73	2.42		
Professional Ethics	NAAC Accredited	83	40.51	2.84	0.91	219
	Non- Accredited	138	40.83	2.31		
Teacher workplace stress Total	NAAC Accredited	83	199.42	8.65	2.59*	219
	Non- Accredited	138	202.46	8.33		

(*Significance level 0.05.)

(*Significance level 0.01.)

Fig. 3: Comparison of Mean and Standard Deviation for teacher's workplace stress of more experienced teacher educators of NAAC Accredited and Non-Accredited teacher education institutions

Table 3. The mean, standard deviation and 't' values of overall teacher's workplace stress and dimensions of teacher's workplace stress as individual insight, relationship status, work life balance, performed responsibilities and professional ethics has been shown in the table. It reveals that more-experienced teacher educators of both NAAC accredited and non-accredited teacher education institutions had different mean scores on teacher's workplace stress. The first dimension (Individual insight) and second dimension (Relationship status) of teacher's workplace stress was significant at the (0.05) level of confidence and other three dimensions of teacher's workplace stress was found not significant. The values of 't' for individual insight, relationship status, work life balance, performed responsibilities and professional ethics aspects were 2.58*, 2.45*, 0.76, 1.85 and 0.91 respectively and for overall teacher's workplace stress was 2.59*. The 't' values for the first dimension, second dimension and for overall teacher's workplace stress of more experienced teacher educators of teacher education institutions was found significant at the (0.05) level of confidence. So, the hypothesis that "There is no significant difference between more experienced teacher educators of NAAC accredited and non-accredited teacher education institutions in relation stress" rejected.

H.4. There is no significant difference between less experienced teacher educators of NAAC accredited and non-accredited teacher education institutions in relation to stress.

Mean and standard deviation of teacher's workplace stress of teacher educators of teacher education institutions have been described in the Table- 4.

Table 4: Differential statistics of teacher's workplace stress of less experienced teacher educators of NAAC Accredited and Non-Accredited teacher education institutions

Table 4						
Dimensions	NAAC Status	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	df
Individual Insight	NAAC Accredited	75	38.20	3.37	2.76**	179

	Non- Accredited	106	39.47	2.82		
Relationship Status	NAAC Accredited	75	39.35	3.19	0.95	179
	Non- Accredited	106	39.75	2.57		
Worklife Balance	NAAC Accredited	75	40.00	2.80	1.55	179
	Non- Accredited	106	40.60	2.42		
Performed Responsibilities	NAAC Accredited	75	39.44	3.34	2.21*	179
	Non- Accredited	106	40.43	2.71		
Professional Ethics	NAAC Accredited	75	40.35	3.03	1.31	179
	Non- Accredited	106	40.85	2.13		
Teacher workplace stress Total	NAAC Accredited	75	197.33	12.94	2.45*	179
	Non- Accredited	106	201.11	7.79		

(*Significance level 0.05.)

(*Significance level 0.01.)

Fig. 4: Comparison of Mean and Standard Deviation for teacher's workplace stress of less experienced teacher educators of NAAC Accredited and Non-Accredited teacher education institutions

Table 4. The mean, standard deviation and 't' values of overall teacher's workplace stress and dimensions of teacher's workplace stress as individual insight, relationship status, work life balance, performed responsibilities and professional ethics has been shown in the table. It reveals that less-experienced teacher educators of both NAAC accredited and non-accredited teacher education institutions had different mean scores on teacher's workplace stress. The first dimension (Individual

insight) of teacher's workplace stress was found significant at the (0.05 and 0.01) level of confidence and fourth dimension (Performed responsibilities) of teacher's workplace stress was found significant at the (0.05) level of confidence and other three dimensions of teacher's workplace stress was found not significant. The values of 't' for individual insight, relationship status, work life balance, performed responsibilities and professional ethics aspects were 2.76**, 0.95, 1.55, 2.21* and 1.31 respectively and for overall teacher's workplace stress was 2.45*. The 't' values for the first dimension, fourth dimension and for overall teacher's workplace stress of less experienced teacher educators of NAAC Accredited and non-Accredited teacher education institutions was found significant at the (0.05) level of confidence. So, the hypothesis that " There is no significant difference between less experienced teacher educators of NAAC accredited and non-accredited teacher education institutions in relation to stress" rejected.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

1. There is difference in Teacher's workplace stress between male teacher educators of NAAC Accredited and non-Accredited teacher education institutions. Male teacher educators of non-Accredited teacher education institutions scored higher in comparison to male teacher educators of NAAC Accredited teacher education institutions.
2. There is difference in Teacher Effectiveness between female teacher educators of NAAC Accredited and non-Accredited teacher education institutions. Female teacher educators of non-Accredited teacher education institutions scored higher in comparison to female teacher educators of NAAC Accredited teacher education institutions.
3. There is difference in Teacher Effectiveness between more experienced teacher educators of NAAC Accredited and non-Accredited teacher education institutions. More experienced teacher educators of non-Accredited teacher education institutions scored higher in comparison to more experienced teacher educators of NAAC Accredited teacher education institutions.
4. There is difference in Teacher Effectiveness between less experienced teacher educators of NAAC Accredited and non-Accredited teacher education institutions. Less experienced teacher educators of non-Accredited teacher education institutions scored higher in comparison to less experienced teacher educators of NAAC Accredited teacher education institutions.

EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS

Based on the results, the following conclusions are drawn to the advantage of head of departments, administrators, teacher educators, pre-service teachers, and the educational system:

1. It is found that teacher educators of non-Accredited teacher education institutions scored higher on teacher's workplace stress scale in comparison to teacher educators of NAAC Accredited teacher education institutions in all dimensions as individual insight, relationship status, work life balance, performed responsibilities and professional ethics significantly and non-significantly. It means teacher educators of non-Accredited teacher education institutions are facing heavy stress than the teacher educators of NAAC Accredited teacher education institutions.
2. The reason why teacher educators of non-accredited teacher education institutions are more stressed in comparison to teacher educators of NAAC Accredited teacher education institutions may be under stress due to the fact that the official and teaching work has not been divided properly. Teacher educators at non-accredited teacher education institutions may be under stress due to their workload. Apart from this, it is also possible that the salary may not be received as per norms or on time.
3. Teacher's workplace stress can have profound effects on various aspects of their professional

and personal lives, as well as on their students and the broader educational environment.

4. NAAC Accreditation ought to be compulsory for every teacher education institution, and such institutions where NAAC Accreditation has not yet been completed should get the Accreditation done as soon as possible.

CONCLUSION OF THE STUDY

This study was conducted to find out the workplace stress of teacher educators of NAAC Accredited and non-Accredited teacher education institutions. It is concluded from the findings that the workplace stress of teacher educators of non-accredited teacher education institutions higher significantly. The effects of stress on teacher educators are far-reaching and can significantly impact their health, professional effectiveness, and personal lives. Addressing teacher stress requires a comprehensive approach that includes support from administrators, professional development opportunities, workload management, and the promotion of a positive work-life balance. Thus, the significance of NAAC accreditation for teacher education institutes is highlighted by this study. Numerous intriguing findings from the current study will undoubtedly increase the body of information that is beneficial to the field of educational research.

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